

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of copper-, cobalt- and nickel(II) complexes with Schiff bases

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A few complexes of Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been prepared by reacting their metal(II) chlorides with 3-(4'-phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2'-hydroxy-1'-iminomethylphenyl)urea and with 3-(4'-phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2',4'-dihydroxy/2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro-1'-methylimino-methylphenyl)ureas (Schiff bases) in ethanol medium. The chelates are coloured solids and non-electrolytes of the type ML₂. The IR spectra of the ligands and complexes suggest involvement of *o*-hydroxy group, carbonyl group, azomethine group in bonding through oxygen and nitrogen atoms respectively. The electronic spectra and magnetic data suggest the octahedral stereochemistry for all the complexes in which metal(II) ion exhibits coordination number six. The ligands and complexes have been tested for their antimicrobial activity.

Schiff bases containing polyfunctional groups offer many practical advantages and unique structural environment for complexation¹. In particular, semicarbazides and semicarbazones have interesting ligational properties and are proved to be promising chelating agents for a number of transitional elements². The orthohydroxybenzaldehydes or acetophenones on reacting with semicarbazides yield the Schiff bases containing an active OH group in addition to the C=O and C=N coordinating groups and it has been shown that all the three groups are involved in the bond formation with transition metal ion in the complex³. The semicarbazones⁴ and the thiazoles⁵ possess various biological activities.

We report here the synthesis, characterization and an-

timicrobial activity of some Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with the semicarbazones containing thiazole nucleus (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

All these complexes (Table 1) are soluble in DMSO and DMF. All the chelates are amorphous, stable in air and have m.ps. around 300°. The elemental analyses confirm to the 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the type ML₂. The molar conductance values in DMF and DMSO (10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) in the range of 2.16–4.24 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, indicate that all the chelates are non-electrolytes. IR spectra of the ligands revealed bands at 3248–3104, (NH) and 1711–1662 cm⁻¹ (C=O)⁶. It has been well established that the formation of intramolecular

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes*

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Color	Metal % Found (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Mol. cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹		μ _{eff} B.M.
					DMF	DMSO	
8a	CuC ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄ S ₂	Green	8.78 (8.61)	298d	2.27	2.81	1.85
8b	CoC ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄ S ₂	Brown	8.36 (8.04)	295d	3.65	2.51	4.94
8c	NiC ₃₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄ S ₂	Brown	7.82 (8.01)	281d	2.64	3.12	2.95
9a	CuC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₆ S ₂	Green	8.13 (7.96)	308	2.16	2.65	1.87
9b	CoC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₆ S ₂	Brown	7.18 (7.43)	287	4.24	3.04	5.10
9c	NiC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₆ S ₂	Brown	7.58 (7.40)	297	2.27	2.67	3.17
10a	CuC ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ O ₄ S ₂	Green	7.41 (7.61)	>310	2.42	2.82	1.88
10b	CoC ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ O ₄ S ₂	Brown	7.46 (7.10)	>310	4.10	3.14	5.21
10c	NiC ₃₆ H ₂₈ N ₈ Cl ₂ O ₄ S ₂	Yellow	7.23 (7.07)	>310	2.56	2.40	3.20

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Scheme 1

hydrogen bonding results in weakening and broadening of the band attributable to OH and also shifts to lower frequency⁷. The ligand band at 2875–2746 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the intramolecular hydrogen-bonded OH stretch⁷ with nitrogen atom of azomethine group. The disappearance of these bands in the spectra of the complexes confirms the formation of covalent bond between oxygen atom and metal ion⁸. The ν_{NH} ligand band⁹ remained unperturbed in the complexes, indicating that NH groups did not participate in bond formation with the metal ions. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ligand band suffered negative shift by 63–62 cm⁻¹ in these complexes, indicating the bonding of C=O group to the metal ions through oxygen atom¹⁰. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ ligand band (1276–1269 cm⁻¹)⁶ shifted considerably towards high frequency side in the complexes at 1348–1311 cm⁻¹. This high frequency shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ phenolic band confirms the formation of covalent bond between oxygen atom of phenolic-OH and metal ion through deprotonation. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ stretch of (azomethine) ligand band¹¹ was observed at 1610–1580 cm⁻¹. The shift of this $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band by 43–31 cm⁻¹ towards lower frequency side¹² in these complexes suggests the coordination between nitrogen of the azomethine group and metal.

Metal-ligand vibrations are generally located in the

region 600–250 cm⁻¹. The skeletal vibrations of the ligand appearing in this region complicate the interpretation. However, comparison of the complex and ligand spectra allowed the assignment of metal sensitive bands. The assignments are purely tentative and are based on previous assignments¹³. In the present case, we have assigned the band at 598–533 to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and 463–400 cm⁻¹ to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ in the complexes.

The observed magnetic moment values for the Cu^{II} complexes (Table 1) are devoid of any spin interactions with distorted octahedral geometry¹⁴. For the Co^{II} complexes, the magnetic moment values are within the expected range (4.30–5.20 B.M.) for Co^{II} complexes of octahedral geometry. For the Ni^{II} complexes, the observed magnetic moments are well within in the range of reported values for hexacoordinated octahedral Ni^{II} complexes (2.83–4.00 B.M.)¹⁵.

Electronic spectra : The broad bands observed in the electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes at 13513–16666 cm⁻¹ assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{2g}$ transitions, are in conformity with expected tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry¹⁶. The broadness of the band may be due to dynamic Jahn-Teller distortion. The spectra of the Co^{II} chelates showed two spin-allowed transitions at 16666–17857 and 21739–22306 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively, and are in conformity with the expected octahedral stereochemistry for Co^{II} ion¹⁷. The appearance of two bands in the spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes at 16625–16000, 22306–20833 cm⁻¹ are assigned¹⁸ to ${}^3A_{2g}(P) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry for the Ni^{II} complexes.

Thermal analysis : The Co^{II} chelate $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_8\text{O}_4\text{S}_2)$ was stable at room temperature. The first weight-loss started at 81° and ended at 180° by the expulsion of NH fragment to get $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{S}_2)$ with the mass-loss of 2.10% on the TG curve (theor. 2.04%). The resultant species started further decomposition at 190° and ended at 481° to get species $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}_2)$ and lost another NH fragment with 1.80% mass-loss on TG curve (theor. 2.09%). This resultant species started further decomposition at 487° to lose organic part and continued beyond 700° forming cobalt(II) oxide and no further inflection temperature was indicated on TG curve.

The Ni^{II} chelate $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_8\text{O}_4\text{S}_2)$ was stable at room temperature. The first weight-loss started at 65° and ended at 460° by the expulsion of two molecules of carbon monoxide and two hydrogen atoms to yield $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}_2)$ with 8.03% mass-loss on TG curve

(theor. 7.29%). The organic part of the species started further decomposition at 473° and ended at 625° to yield Ni(C₃₂H₂₄N₄O₂S₂) by the elimination of two molecules of nitrogen with a mass-loss of 7.38% on the TG curve (theor. 8.30%). This species continued to decompose beyond 700° to form nickel oxide as residue and no further inflection temperature was indicated on the TG curve.

The IR spectral observations suggest the involvement of C=O and C=N in the coordination for these complexes. The electronic and magnetic data suggest the octahedral stereochemistry for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} complexes and distorted octahedral stereochemistry for Cu^{II} complexes.

All the ligands and their complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, at 10 mg/ml concentration and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* at the same concentration using Gentamycin and Nystatin as the standard drugs. All the ligands **4**, **5a**, **5b** were found to be less active than the standards. Complexes **9a**, **9b**, **10a** and **10b** displayed comparable activity with that of standard drug.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses were performed by microanalytical methods at Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore. Cu, Co and Ni were determined gravimetrically as salicylaldoxinate, oxinate and dimethyl glyoximate, respectively. Conductance was measured on an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. The magnetic moment was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a calibrant. The electronic spectra (DMSO) were taken on a Systronics 119 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1000 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆ unless otherwise stated) on a Bruker (400 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. TGA was obtained on a Mettler Toledo Star instrument with a flow rate 100 ml/min. Antibacterial activity of the compounds were assessed against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and the antifungal activity against *A. niger* by cup-plate diffusion method.

Preparation of ligands :

The starting material 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole (**1**) was prepared according to the reported method¹⁹.

Ethyl 4-phenylthiazole-2-carbamate (2) : Compound **1** (1 g, 0.00568 mol) was dissolved in minimum amount of pyridine and cooled to 0° under anhydrous conditions. Ethyl chloroformate (0.6316 g, 0.00568 mol) was added to it dropwise at 0–2° while stirring under anhydrous condi-

tions. The mixture was stirred at this temperature for 1 h and further 0.5 h at room temperature. It was refluxed for 12 h on a water-bath. The mixture was then decomposed by pouring in ice-water and pyridine removed by steam distillation. The resulting solid was dried and crystallized from absolute ethanol, (44%), m.p. 156–158° (Found : C, 58.09; H, 4.88; N, 11.34. C₁₂H₁₂N₂O₂S reqd. : C, 58.06; H, 4.84; N, 11.29%); ν_{\max} 3161 (NH), 1718 (C=O), 1578 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 9.31 (1H, s, NH), 7.26–7.82 (5H, m, ArH), 7.09 (1H, s, H at 5th position of thiazole), 4.25 (2H, q, CH₂), 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃).

4-Phenylthiazole-2-semicarbazide (3) : A suspension of **2** (3.47 g, 0.0153 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (5 ml, 80%) for 5 h on a water-bath and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting white solid was dried and crystallized from ethanol, (48%), m.p. 220–221° d; (Found : C, 51.31; H, 4.19; N, 23.99, C₁₀H₁₀N₄OS reqd. : C, 51.28; H, 4.27; N, 23.93%); ν_{\max} 3340, 3273, 3112 (NH/NH₂), 1681 (C=O), 1594 (C=N) and 655 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C).

3-(4'-Phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2'-hydroxy-1'-iminomethyl)/(2',4'-dihydroxy/2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro-1'-methyliminomethyl)phenylureas (4, 5a, 5b) : A mixture of **3** (1.17 g, 0.005 mol), salicylaldehyde (0.6096 g, 0.005 mol) and appropriate *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (0.005 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) with catalytic amount of conc. HCl (1–2 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The solid separated out was washed with alcohol, dried and crystallized from ethanol to get **4**, **5a** and **5b**, respectively : **4** (94%), m.p. 209–210° (Found : C, 60.39; H, 4.11; N, 16.51. C₁₇H₁₄N₄O₂S reqd. : C, 60.35; H, 4.14; N, 16.56%); ν_{\max} 3154, 3104 (NH/NH), 2746 (hydrogen bonded OH), 1711 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1552 (thiazole C=N), 1269 (phenolic C–O) and 675 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); δ (CDCl₃) 11.09 (1H, b s, OH), 10.10 (1H, b s, NH), 9.01 (1H, b s, NH), 7.23–8.33 (10H, m, N=CH, 9 ArH), 6.91 (1H, s, H at 5th position of thiazole); **5a** (60%), 224–226° (Found : C, 58.73; H, 4.29; N, 15.26. C₁₈H₁₆N₄O₃S reqd. : C, 58.69; H, 4.34; N, 15.2%); ν_{\max} 3341 (OH), 3248, 3114 (NH/NH), 2875 (hydrogen bonded OH), 1662 (C=O), 1580 (C=N), 1546 (thiazole C=N), 1269 (phenolic C–O) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); δ (CDCl₃) 12.82 (1H, b s, OH), 10.81 (1H, s, OH), 10.00 (1H, s, NH), 9.81 (1H, s, NH), 6.28–7.95 (9H, m, 8 ArH + H at 5th position of thiazole), 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃); **5b** (90%), m.p. 228–229° (Found : C, 55.92; H, 3.91; N, 14.39. C₁₈H₁₅N₄ClO₂S reqd. : C, 55.88; H, 3.88; N, 14.48%); ν_{\max} 3201, 3114 (NH/NH), 2778 (hydrogen bonded OH), 1706 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1532 (thiazole C=N), 1276 (phenolic C–O) and 679 cm⁻¹ (S–C–S).

Metal complexes : To an ethanolic solution containing

3-(4'-phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2'-hydroxy-1'-iminomethylphenyl)urea (**4**), 3-(4'-phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2',4'-dihydroxy-1'-methyliminomethylphenyl)urea (**5a**) and 3-(4'-phenylthiazole-2'-yl)-1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-chloro-1'-methyliminomethylphenyl)urea (**5b**) (0.002 mol), the metal chlorides (0.002 mol) were added. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for ~2 h on a steam-bath, then sodium acetate (2 g) was added to it and refluxed for further 3 h. It was then poured in distilled water. The resulting solid complexes were washed with distilled water and ethanol, and dried (yields 78–88%).

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